

ing with 66 hills/m² in wet season, but was higher at 15- × 20-cm spacing in dry season.

Panicle weights from treatments of 33 and 22 hills were comparable in both

seasons. Panicle weight for 66 hills was the lowest.

Deep placement utilizes more labor at conventional spacing. Using the modified 15 × 20 cm spacing reduced the

number of planting sites 50%, and therefore reduced seed and planting costs 50%. These savings will compensate for the extra labor needed for USG deep placement. □

Multiplication of azolla in alkaline soils of Punjab

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Azolla may be a substitute for nitrogen fertilizer in wetland rice, but its multiplication and growth are determined by soils and environmental factors. We studied azolla growth patterns in a subtropical alkaline soil at the PAU farm in Ludhiana.

Six concrete tanks (2 × 2.2 m) were filled to 15 cm with a sandy loam soil with pH 8.4. A 15–20 cm water level above the soil was maintained. Tanks were inoculated with 250 g of a local azolla species in Jun 1979. Superphosphate at 1.75 kg P/ha per week was applied to each tank. The temperature of the top 0-2 cm of water in the tank was recorded daily at 1500 hours. Azolla growth and N fixation were monitored every 2 weeks throughout the year.

Growth rate of azolla in tanks as affected by temperature.

Azolla harvested in Mar, Apr, and Oct weighed 10-13 t fresh matter/ha per month and contained 30 kg N/ha. Fresh matter and total N varied from 0.3 to 4.2 t and 0.8–10.7 kg N/ha per month for other months. Azolla produced 55 t/ha per year, which contained about 139 kg N.

Azolla grew slowly from Jun to Sep, which is the rice season, because of high ambient temperatures (see figure). High standing water temperatures (34–39 °C) from May to Sep and low temperatures (16–21 °C) from Dec to Feb reduced azolla growth. Azolla species with high temperature tolerance need to be tested. □

Rock phosphate-pyrite mixture: a good substitute for single superphosphate

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Use of inexpensive, readily available fertilizers without sacrificing yield is top priority. From kharif 1979 to 1981 we compared yields from neutral and alkaline rice fields fertilized with a basal application of a single superphosphate with those of fields treated with a 1:5 rock phosphate-pyrite mixture. Both treatments received 26.4 kg P/ha.

Trials were conducted at the Regional Research Station at Mandya on a sandy loam Alfisol (pH 6.9, Olsen's P 8.5 kg/ha, and CEC 16.8 meq/100 g) and at the Agricultural Research Station at

Direct and residual effect of rock phosphate-pyrite mixture on grain yield (av of 3 seasons).^a

Treatment	Yield (t/ha) (av 3 seasons)		P uptake in rough rice (kg/ha)		% recovery in rough rice		Olsen's P (kg/ha) after 3 seasons (RRS, Mandya -NS)	Residual effect on grain yield (P treated plot-control) t/ha (RRS, Mandya -NS)
	Mandya (NS)	Siruguppa (HS)	NS	HS	NS	HS		
Control (no P)	4.1	3.6	11.5	7.6	—	—	8.7	—
Single superphosphate at 26.4 kg P/ha	4.9	4.7	15.2	11.8	11.4	15.2	9.4	0.8
Rock phosphate – pyrite mixture (1:5) at 26.4 kg P/ha	5.2	4.9	17.9	13.2	22.7	21.7	12.0	1.1
F Test	*	**						*
CD (0.05)	0.67	0.81						0.48
CV (%)	12.1	10.3						14.6

^aNS = neutral soil, HS = high pH soil.

Siruguppa on a silty clay Vertisol (pH 8.6, Olsen's P 6.2 kg/ha, and CEC 24.2 meq/100 g). Recommended agronomic pro-

cedures were used for the transplanted crops, and Prakash (IET2254) was grown. The Mussoorie rock phosphate used